

Sachchai

also known as “Charismatic Healing Movement”, “New Religious Movement”, “Faith-based Group”

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Entry tags: Religious Group, New Religious Movement (NRM), Syncretic Religions

Sachchai is a loosely organized group of believers who aim to heal their suffering and illnesses through the means of Bible study, ritual exorcism, and speaking in tongue. Sachchai is rapidly spreading across villages and towns in Nepal. Hundreds of thousands of believers have embraced it. More than ninety percent of the believers are women who mostly are from poor and low-caste backgrounds. Sachchai claims to be an inclusive, egalitarian, and universal group. People from any religious and cultural background are welcome and they do not need to abandon their past religions and cultures. But the believers are required to believe in Jesus and study the Bible. Other syncretist faith-based groups like Sachchai are also found in South Asia. For example, Christ-Bhakta followers in Tamil Nadu, India, who identify themselves as Christ-Bhakta Hindus, and Jesus Imandars in Bangladesh, who identify themselves as Isa-Muslims (Jørgensen 2008; Kuttiyanikkal 2014). Both these groups study the Bible but do not disassociate themselves from their past religions. Sachchai was established by Christian evangelicals in the late 1970s in India but could not prosper until the first decade of the 21st century when it got fertile ground in Nepal. Extreme political instabilities, huge international labor migration of men, dire lack of public services, and, most importantly, rising domestic violence against women, all have contributed to the rapid expansion of Sachchai. Hindu nationalists and Christians in Nepal both have considered Sachchai as a threat to them.

Date Range: 1975 CE - 2020 CE

Region: Nepal and parts of North India

Region tags: South Asia, Nepal, India

Nepal and parts of North India

Status of Participants:

✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

– Source 1: There is no any print sources so far for understanding Sachchai. Please see the note.

– Source 2: <https://www.setopati.com/social/169766>

Notes: Neither Sachchai nor any other scholars have published anything so far. Since the movement has come to public's attention only very recently, about 10 years ago. There is no any academic publication so far. The main leader of Sachchai said the movement did not want to use any form of media (print or electronic such as TV) to spread the movement's message or to inform about the movement. Despite his claim, believers in Nepal use Facebook and YouTube pages to spread the movement's messages. A few Nepali medium local newspapers have covered the news about Sachchai, but the news are mostly negative blaming Sachchai for Christianization. One such news under Source 2 reports about how Sachchai believers celebrate/worship Hindu festivals while pronouncing the name of Jesus.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: <https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCJciQdMbWCr-hPmVWu9HVyw>

– Source 1 Description: This is the YouTube page of one of the largest groups of Sachchai in Nepal. They share videos of testimonies, educational speeches, and other programs. There are tens of such videos in this YouTube page.,

– Source 2 URL: <https://www.facebook.com/Sachhaikendra-Nepal-2186630364921086>

– Source 2 Description: This Facebook page, with about 1,500 followers, is used to communicate with believers and also to disseminate the movement's messages.

Notes: Sachchai as a single community of religion does not have an official website. There are dozens of Sachchai groups who have their own Facebook and YouTube pages. The YouTube and Facebook pages provided here belong to the central branch of one of the biggest groups, Ishwaria Marga Bhajan Mandal Sachchai Kendra Nepal, Pokhara, Nepal. This group has more than 100 branches across Nepal and most of the branches have their own Facebook pages.

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

– Source 1 URL: <https://www.facebook.com/Sachhaikendra-Nepal-2186630364921086>

– Source 1 Description: This is the Facebook page of one of the biggest groups of Sachchai in Nepal, used to communicate with believers and dissemination of Sachchai messages. The page has about 1,500 followers. Sachchai post important information, videos, and pictures in the page.

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: Although Sachchai dissociates itself from Christianity, it borrows ideas and practices from Christianity, especially from Pentecostalism. Believers mostly come from Hindu and Buddhist backgrounds and they are allowed to continue to follow certain rituals and festivals of their past religion and cultures. So there is a cultural contact between Christianity, Hinduism, and Buddhism with Sachchai.

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

– Yes

Notes: The cultural contact is not only competitive but also antagonistic. Christians and Sachchai believers in Nepal dismiss each other's validity and existence. While Christians blame Sachchai for spreading "false message" of the Bible by allowing believers to practice Hindu rituals and festivals, Sachchai blames Christians for restricting the opportunity to study the Bible to only Christians. Both groups claim to be the true believers of God. Additionally, general Hindus and particularly Hindu nationalists vehemently oppose Sachchai, blaming it for Christianizing Nepal.

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Yes

Notes: Sachchai welcomes believers from other religious backgrounds such as Christianity, Hinduism, Buddhism, and Islam, and the believers are allowed to continue to practice most of their cultural and religious rituals and festivals. Most believers are from Hinduism, and they continue to follow their Hindu festivals and rituals. For example, death rituals are performed according to Hindu rituals. Hindu festivals of Dashain, Tihar, and Teej are celebrated. However, Christians in Nepal are very strict in terms of their cultural practices. They do not even put red power on their forehead, do not celebrate Hindu festivals, and do not follow any Hindu rituals of birth, marriage, and death.

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– No

Notes: Cultural contact is competitive and antagonistic. As mentioned above, Sachchai has been a target of criticisms from other religious groups in Nepal. Such criticisms mostly have political overtones.

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– Yes

Notes: The relationship between Sachchai and Hindu organizations is conflictual. Sachchai has experienced some level of violent opposition from believers and activists of other religious groups. For example, Hindu believers and activists have physically a few destructed Sachchai buildings, have beaten a few Sachchai leaders, and locked a few Sachchai buildings. Hindu activists' stated reason is "sound pollution" because of the sound produced from Sachchai's prayer meetings. The main reason, which is unstated, is political: they don't want Sachchai to grow in Nepal. Sachchai's relationship with Christians, however, has remained peaceful so far, although the relationship is antagonistic.

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– No

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Yes

Notes: An oral declaration that one believes in God is what makes one a believer. Believers self-identify themselves as a member. There is no official record system or any other identification system that can identify who is a member or who is not. Sachchai has no monitoring system. Anyone can enter a Sachchai building and attend Sachchai meetings.

↳ Assigned at birth (membership is default for this society):

– No

↳ Assigned by personal choice:

– Yes

Notes: Membership is assigned based entirely on the personal choice of a believer.

↳ Assigned by class:

– No

↳ Assigned at a specific age:

– No

↳ Assigned by gender:

– No

Notes: Although the membership is not assigned by gender, more than 90 percent of the members of Sachchai are women. The overwhelming participation of women in Sachchai is not entirely new. Scholars have observed in many parts of the world that charismatic Christianity such as Pentecostalism has mostly disproportionately attracted women. There is a vast literature on Pentecostalism and women. In the South Asian context, Nathaniel Roberts (2016) and Sarbeswar Sahoo (2018) have observed similar attraction of women to Pentecostalism. Women mostly embrace Sachchai because of domestic/spousal violence, illnesses and diseases, and the country's worst public services. Among the three, an increasing experience of gender abuse and violence from their husbands and in-laws stands out. Husbands of most women have migrated to foreign countries for labor. Women left behind home run the family, but mostly take care of the children. Most women have also migrated to urban areas to educate their children in boarding schools. These women hence come under the surveillance of their husbands, relatives, and neighbors for their supposedly sexual looseness. Thus the absence of husbands and ensuing loneliness of women in urban areas, increasing responsibilities, and bad relationships with their husbands have afflicted many women in Nepal.

↳ Assigned by participation in a particular ritual:

– Yes

Notes: In order to become members of Sachchai, participants need to recite a verse from the Bible (administered by a Sachchai leader) (Roman 10: 9): "If you declare with your mouth, "Jesus is Lord," and believe in your heart that God raised him from the dead, you will be saved." They don't need to be baptized as Christians do.

↳ Assigned by some other factor:

– No

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– No

Notes: Proselytization has been made illegal in Nepal, punishable by five years of imprisonment for a Nepali citizen, and by expulsion within seven days for a foreign national. Preaching has been also made illegal. These laws are murky and the Christian population becomes an easy victim of such laws. Any Christian traveling with a Bible or any Christian administering a Baptism could be easily accused of converting. Therefore, Sachchai is very cautious about spreading its messages and about preaching. Generally, prospective members hear about Sachchai from other members and from their neighbors and relatives, and they themselves approach Sachchai.

Does the religion have official political support

– No

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Members can denounce Sachchai easily, just by not going to attend Sachchai prayer meetings. Many believers denounce Sachchai after they get dissatisfied with it, when either their problems are not addressed by Sachchai or, sometimes contrarily, when their problems are addressed.

Are apostates prosecuted or punished:

– No

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 500000

Notes: There is no formal or official record of the number of believers. Sachchai leaders highly inflate the number. They often claim that they comprise one-third of Nepal's population, which is about 9 million.

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Estimated population, percentage of sample region: 1.6

Nature of religious group [please select one]:

– Small religious group (not related to larger religious group)

Notes: Sachchai is an independent syncretist religious group although the believers study the Bible and follow Jesus Christ. However, the general public and Hindu activists consider Sachchai as a denomination of Christianity.

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

Is there a hierarchy among these leaders:

– Yes

Notes: Unlike in Christianity and Hinduism, there is a weak hierarchy between the leaders in Sachchai. Although there is some hierarchy in organizational structure, every believer is supposed to have equal healing or divine power.

↳ A single leader of a local community:

– No

↳ Multiple religious communities each with its own leader, no hierarchy among these leaders:

– Yes

↳ "Regional" leaders who oversee one or more local leader(s) (e.g. bishops):

– No

↳ A single leader for the religious group that oversees all other leaders in the sample region:

– No

↳ A council or group of leaders for the religious group that oversees all other leaders in the sample region:

– No

↳ Estimate how many levels there are in the hierarchy of religious leadership:

– Number of levels [numeric value]: 3

Notes: There are many independent groups of Sachchai. Each group has three tiers of leaders--the main leader of a group, a branch leader, and other leaders within a branch.

↳ Are leaders believed to possess supernatural powers or qualities:

– Yes

Notes: Divine power is supposed to be automatically received from God. The degree of belief and devotion to God is supposed to determine how much power one receives from God. Every believer can receive divine power.

↳ Powers are acquired by individual deeds carried out in past lives:

– No

↳ Powers are acquired by individual deeds carried out in the current life:

– No

↳ Powers are inherited:

– No

↳ Powers are culturally transmitted from a supernatural being:

– Yes

↳ Powers are culturally transmitted from another human (e.g. teacher):

– No

↳ Powers are associated with leadership office they assume:

– No

↳ Are religious leaders chosen:

– Yes

Notes: Leaders are chosen on the basis of their speaking skills (edifying speech), the commitment of time, and ability to open a branch. If a believer wants to open a branch in her/his village, she/he automatically becomes the (branch) leader.

↳ A leader chooses his/her own replacement:

– No

↳ A leader's retinue or ministers chooses the new leader:

– No

↳ Other leaders in the religious group choose that leader:

– Yes

↳ A political leader chooses the leader:

– No

↳ Other members of the leader's congregation choose the leader:

– No

↳ All members of the religious group in the sample region participate in choosing the leader:

– No

↳ Communication with supernatural power(s) believed to be part of the selection process:

– No

↳ Are leaders considered fallible:

– Yes

Notes: Leaders are considered as similar to any other human being, who can commit mistakes. Fallibility is, however, explained in terms of devil's work. A devil can cast a spell on the leaders and can make them make mistakes.

↳ Charges of fallibility made by a leader's own followers:

– No

↳ Charges of fallibility made by other leaders in the religious group:

– No

↳ Charges of fallibility made by a political ruler:

– No

↳ Are close followers or disciples of a religious leader required to obediently and unquestionably accept the leader's pronouncements on all matters:

– No

Notes: Believers are free to profess their own religious practices, follow their political beliefs. Believers are not required to unquestionably follow the leaders in most of the matters.

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also "oral scriptures" (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

Notes: Sachchai uses the Bible as its key religious text. Unlike Pentecostal Christians, Sachchai believers consider the Bible as open to interpretation and fallible. Everything written in the Bible is not believed to be true or good. The Bible is equated to a river that contains both dirt and fishes, both good and bad things. Hence, it is believed that it is up to a believer to choose good things and discard bad things from the Bible. But it is not openly told which things are bad in the Bible.

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

↳ Are they oral:

– No

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– Yes

↳ Revealed by a high god:

– No

Notes: Sachchai believes that the Bible was not revealed by God. It believes that the text was written by humans but through the guidance of God.

↳ Revealed by other supernatural being:

– No

↳ Inspired by high god:

– No

↳ Inspired by other supernatural being:

– Yes

Notes: Sachchai believes that the Bible was inspired by God, written by the instruction of God.

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings:

– No

↳ Originated from non-divine human being:

– No

↳ Are the scriptures alterable:

– No

Notes: But Sachchai considers that the passages of the Bible are open to interpretation.

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting the scriptures:

– No

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures:

– No

Notes: Unlike in Churches, Sachchai does not formally teach the Bible to its leaders and believers. The leaders self-educate the Bible through self-study and watching Youtube videos and Christian TV programs. Many leaders are illiterate or semi-literate who even can't read the

Bible, but they teach the Bible through memorization of certain passages.

Is there a codified canon of scriptures:

– No

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– No

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Is iconography present:

– No

Notes: Sachchai believers do not use even the image/photo of Jesus Christ. They discourage any use of image, idol, or painting in the name of God, probably because they criticize the Hindu worship of idols and images.

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– No

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer “no” only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is not clear to me whether Sachchai believers care about this distinction.

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: Sachchai believers believe that people go to either Heaven or Hell based on whether one

believed in God or not. Those believed in God are supposed to be rescued by God and taken to Heaven.

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Heaven and Hell are the two locations one will end up after a death.

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world:

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined “above” space:

– No

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined “below” space:

– No

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined horizontal space:

– No

↳ Afterlife located in "other" space:

– No

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Notes: Sachchai believers do not believe in reincarnation in this world. They believe in the resurrection from death in the same way Jesus was resurrected by God.

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– No

Notes: There is no any guideline on how to treat adherent's corpses. Believers treat the corpses according to their own past religious traditions and rituals.

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– No

Notes: Sachchai believers have different burial practices, based on their religious backgrounds. Sachchai does not have its distinct burial practice.

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Notes: Belief in supernatural beings is one of the central ideas of Sachchai. Sachchai adherents believe in good and evil spirits. Evil spirits are supposed to be the cause of whatever misfortunes they have in their life. Evil spirits are thought to be present everywhere waiting for an opportune time to hurt human beings. It is believed that evil spirits can be defeated only through a firm belief in God.

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Notes: As in Christianity, Sachchai believes in a single God who can be present in three forms, the Father God, Son of God, and Holy Spirit. Although the believers are free to worship Hindu gods, Hindu gods are often mocked as just idols or stone god, without any power.

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– No

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– No

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:

– No

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:

– Yes

↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:

– No

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:

– No

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can reward:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can punish:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:

– No

↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:

– No

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:

– No

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

Notes: Sachchai followers believe that God communicates with them through dreams. God is believed to guide them through dreams on what to do and what not to do.

↳ In trance possession:

– No

↳ Through divination practices:

– No

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

↳ Only through monarch

– No

↳ Other form of communication with living:

– No

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– No

Notes: I don't think Sachchai believes in the presence of a previously human spirit. Believers believe in the Holy Spirit and the evil spirit. The evil spirit is a non-human spirit.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– No

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

Notes: Non-human supernatural beings, i.e. an evil spirit, are supposed to know every human affair. It is believed that an evil spirit always looking for an opportunity to hurt a person.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have other knowledge of this world:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can reward:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can punish:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– No

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:

– No

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

Notes: The idea of supernatural monitoring is crucial in Sachchai belief. Followers believe that God is omnipresent and he constantly monitors an individual. It is believed that God punishes or rewards an individual according to their actions. In Sachchai the idea of supernatural monitoring helps the followers to self-discipline themselves by keeping them away from immoral activities.

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously "moral" or "ethical" norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– Yes

Notes: Sachchai followers espouse the idea that those who are generous and helpful to the needy people are favored by God. Sachchai followers occasionally raise emergency and relief funds and help people in need.

↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:

– No

Notes: Unlike in Christianity, there is no taboo in food, dress, or rituals within Sachchai belief.

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:

– Yes

Notes: Sachchai followers believe that God condemns any form of murder.

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:

– Yes

Notes: Sachchai followers believe that God condemns any form of murder. They preach for harmony and cooperation among religious groups.

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:

– Yes

Notes: Sachchai followers believe that God condemns any form of murder.

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– Yes

Notes: Sachchai followers believe that God forbids certain sexual relationships such as homosexual relationships and sexual relationships outside marriage.

↳ Adultery:

– Yes

↳ Incest:

– Yes

↳ Other sexual practices:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:

– Yes

Notes: Sachchai followers believe that being true is what makes one a true believer of God. The name of the movement, Sachchai, itself refers to being true.

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:

– No

Notes: Sachchai followers believe that God does not concern about ritual observance. Followers are allowed to observe whatever rituals they want. Followers are from different religious and cultural backgrounds and they observe their own past religious and cultural rituals.

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:

– No

Notes: Sachchai followers believe that God did not create a religion, i.e Christianity, and divided people among various religions. They believe that people do not need any religious association to be a disciple of God or to receive power from God. So Sachchai followers do not believe in conversion to Christianity or converting people to Sachchai.

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

Notes: Sachchai followers believe that God punishes those who do wrong things.

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– No

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: Sachchai followers believe that one will suffer in his/her afterlife if one does not believe in God.

↳ Supernatural punishments in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– No

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as an inferior life form:

– No

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in an inferior realm:

– No

↳ Other [specify]

– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

Notes: Sachchai followers believe that when pleased God rewards (aashish in Nepali) those who believe in him. Pleasing God for his rewards is one of the central ideas in Sachchai. God supposed to be pleased through prayers, remembering him, spreading his words, helping others, and so on.

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:

– Yes

- ↳ Done only by high god:
 - Yes
- ↳ Done by many supernatural beings:
 - No
- ↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:
 - No
- ↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:
 - No
- ↳ Done to enforce group norms:
 - No
- ↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:
 - No
- ↳ Done randomly:
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Supernatural rewards in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:
 - No
 - ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of mild sensory pleasure:
 - No
 - ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory pleasure:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of eternal happiness:
 - Yes

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as a superior life form:
– Yes

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in a superior realm:
– Yes

↳ Other [specify]
– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:
– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:
– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of good luck:
– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of political success or power:
– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of success in battle:
– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of peace or social stability:
– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of healthy crops or good weather:
– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of success on journeys:
– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure:
– No

- ↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure:
 - No
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants:
 - Yes
- ↳ Other [specify]
 - No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– Yes

Notes: Similar to messianic beliefs in Christianity, Sachchai believers also believe in the return of Jesus Christ in an appropriate time to save suffering people from the earth.

- ↳ Is the messiah's whereabouts or time of coming known?
 - No

- ↳ Is the messiah's purpose known:
 - Yes

Notes: The purpose of the messiah is to rescue people who are suffering.

- ↳ Messiah is a political figure who restores political rule:
 - No

- ↳ Messiah is a priestly figure who restores religious traditions:
 - No

- ↳ Other purpose:
 - Yes [specify]: bring peace and prosperity in the society and country.

Is an eschatology present:

– No

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Sachchai prescribes a code of conduct for its believers. In order to be a good believer, one is required to have good virtue. For example, one is required to be polite, honest, patient and one should not engage in activities such as adultery, alcoholism, cheating, stealing.

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– No

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: The central virtue of Sachchai is truth, i.e. being true to everything. The word Sachchai itself is a Nepali/Hindu word, which means truth. Other virtues that Sachchai advocates are politeness, honesty, fairness, honesty, love, care, chastity.

↳ Honesty / trustworthiness / integrity:

– Yes

↳ Courage (in battle):

– No

↳ Courage (generic):

– Yes

↳ Compassion / empathy / kindness / benevolence:

– Yes

↳ Mercy / forgiveness / tolerance:

– Yes

↳ Generosity / charity:

– Yes

- ↳ Selflessness / selfless giving:
 - Yes
- ↳ Righteousness / moral rectitude:
 - Yes
- ↳ Ritual purity / ritual adherence / abstention from sources of impurity:
 - No
- ↳ Respectfulness / courtesy:
 - Yes
- ↳ Familial obedience / filial piety:
 - Yes
- ↳ Fidelity / loyalty:
 - No
- ↳ Cooperation:
 - Yes
- ↳ Independence / creativity / freedom:
 - No
- ↳ Moderation / frugality:
 - Yes
- ↳ Forbearance / fortitude / patience:
 - Yes
- ↳ Diligence / self-discipline / excellence:
 - Yes
- ↳ Assertiveness / decisiveness / confidence / initiative:
 - Yes

- ↳ Strength (physical):
 - No
- ↳ Power / status / nobility:
 - No
- ↳ Humility / modesty:
 - No
- ↳ Contentment / serenity / equanimity:
 - No
- ↳ Joyfulness / enthusiasm / cheerfulness:
 - No
- ↳ Optimism / hope:
 - Yes
- ↳ Gratitude / thankfulness:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reverence / awe / wonder:
 - No
- ↳ Faith / belief / trust / devotion:
 - Yes
- ↳ Wisdom / understanding:
 - No
- ↳ Discernment / intelligence:
 - No
- ↳ Beauty / attractiveness:
 - No

↳ Cleanliness (physical) / orderliness:

– No

↳ Other important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– No

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– Yes

Notes: Certain sexual relationships are prohibited in Sachchai, mostly those outside heterosexual marriages. For example, sex before marriage, extramarital sex, and gay and lesbian sex. In fact, for practical reasons as well, having proper sexual conduct is one key area of personal reform among Sachchai believers. As husbands of most Sachchai women (and other also of other women) live away from home in a foreign country, the women are suspected by thier husbands and neighbors of being sexually loose. So Sachchai leaders stress women's faithfulness to their husbands.

↳ Monogamy (males):

– Yes

↳ Monogamy (females):

– Yes

↳ Other sexual constraints (males):

– Yes

Notes: Sex before and beyond marriage is prohibited.

↳ Other sexual constraints (females):

– Yes

Notes: Sex before and beyond marriage is prohibited.

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– No

Notes: Followers do not need to commit time for the belief. They can attend prayers meetings based on their availability of time. A follower does not necessarily attend prayer meetings. He/she can do prayer at home. This non-commitment of time is one reason Sachchai has been able to attract poor women who needed to remain busy most of the time.

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

i.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– No

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– Yes

Notes: Sachchai followers use various fictive kinship terminologies such as "sister," "father," "husband," and children. For example, they consider themselves children of God and address each other as a sister. Sachchai women address God as a father. Some women also consider God as their true husband.

↳ Fictive kinship terminology universal:

– Yes

↳ Fictive kinship terminology widespread:

– Yes

↳ Fictive kinship terminology employed but uncommon:

– No

Notes: These fictive terminologies such as sister, father, and husband are common in the area where Sachchai is practiced.

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– Other [specify in comments]

Notes: Sachchai can be characterized as a community. Sachchai believers identify themselves as a community of believers, "biswasi jan" in Nepali.

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– Yes

Notes: Sachchai does not have its primary aim to engage in humanitarian and welfare supports, but it occasionally makes small donations to victims of natural disasters, elderly people, homeless, and street children. The support is not regular. The fund is collected from believers during prayer meetings. It does not have big individual or corporate donors like in the western countries.

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– Yes

Notes: Sachchai occasionally raise funds from its followers and then provide relief to the poor and the needy.

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– No

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– No

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

Is extra-religious education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Notes: Sachchai is a community of loosely organized groups of members. Believers gather themselves voluntarily and form an informal group. There is no provision of formal membership and believers can join and leave the group at their will. Recently, as the government of Nepal is giving trouble to them, some groups have registered formally in local administration as non-governmental organizations and followed government guidelines of organizational structures and operations.

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Notes: Sachchai leaders need to often interact with other institutional bureaucracy when conflicts occur between Sachchai and Hindu believers and activists. Hindu activists sometimes vigorously oppose Sachchai and often time they interrupt Sachchai activities. During such times, Sachchai leaders seen local government's help. Additionally, as Sachchai is needed to run according to government policies, they need to interact with the government officials.

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– No

Notes: Although followers are encouraged to make small donations during prayer meetings, there is no compulsion to donate. It is believed that the more one donates, the more he/she receives blessings from God.

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, the followers are subjected to tax according to the tax rules of the Government of Nepal.

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Sachchai leaders sometimes interact with and seek help from the police force when they have conflicts with Hindu activists.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an an

institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Sachchai believers are subject to punishment according to state laws.

Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– No

Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– No

Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– No

Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– No

Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Sachchai adherents are subject to state, provincial, and local governments' legal codes.

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Sachchai believers are allowed to serve in the state army.

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– No

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Sachchai believers use the Nepali calendar.

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– No

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

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